

Bryon Lippincott

Vol 4:1 2024

Payap University, Thailand

ORCID Number: 0009-0008-2195-0116; bryon@bryonlippincott.com

ABSTRACT

This article explores the unlikely convergence of patriarchal beliefs, ideologies, and narratives between traditional Cambodian culture, Christian ideologies, and international political pressures on the Cambodian government. This convergence creates the opportunity for an authoritarian disciplinary approach to social justice and community development interventions to address sex trafficking in Cambodia that denies women the agency to make choices about their bodies and engage in sexual commerce for economic survival or financial gain. It also legitimizes strict control of women during their recovery from sex trafficking, preventing them from contacting their families, denying them freedom of movement, and coercing them to work in social enterprises or state-owned operations as part of their rehabilitation. Government actors and anti-trafficking NGOs use cultural, religious, and political narratives to equate sex work and sex trafficking, resulting in physical violence against women, infringements on their human rights, invasions of their privacy, and their subjection to disciplinary environments in both government and NGO shelters. Narratives identifying women engaging in sexual commerce as trafficking victims without regard for their circumstances and choices is an act of rhetorical violence and social injustice that diminishes their perceived value in society, reduces their access to opportunities and social support systems, and results in increased risks of other forms of violence. This article recommends clarifying anti-trafficking legislation, improving oversight on anti-

trafficking responses and interventions, and improving social and cultural narratives related to sex trafficking.

Keywords: Authoritarian Discipline, Cambodia, Chab Srey, Social Justice, Sex Trafficking

INTRODUCTION

Human trafficking is a form of violence that has increased in frequency over the last two and a half decades. In 2001, estimates indicated that 700,000 – 800,000 people were trafficked worldwide (Clawson, 2007). In 2023, the Global Slavery Index reported that an estimated 50 million people are currently trafficked or exploited in some form of modern slavery (Walk Free, 2023), a 7000% increase in the number of people enslaved over a mere 22 years. Additionally, these numbers do not include the estimated 160 million exploited through child labor practices as of 2021 (International Labor Organization, 2024). Estimates of the prevalence of human trafficking vary across international organizations, NGOs, and governments, but these estimates agree that women and girls are disproportionately vulnerable to sex trafficking. Sex trafficking in Southeast Asia has been a specific area of concern for NGOs, with anti-trafficking efforts in the region focused on eliminating sex trafficking, especially in Thailand, Cambodia, and Vietnam.

Christian NGOs working to eliminate the sexual exploitation of women, girls, and children have historically led social justice and community development efforts to address sex trafficking in Cambodia (Miles et al., 2020). While sex trafficking is an ongoing concern in Cambodia, scholars dispute government and NGO portrayals of the scale of the problem and their proposed solutions (Keo et al., 2014; Overs, 2013; Steinfatt, 2011).

Cambodia is officially a constitutional monarchy that operates as a parliamentary representative democracy (United States Department of State, 2011). Prime Minister Hun Manet, son of long-time prime minister and authoritarian ruler Hun Sen (The Associated Press, 2024), operates as an authoritarian leader despite Cambodia being a representative democracy (Lawrence, 2020; Luo & Un, 2022). Hun Sen and his ruling party have maintained control through violence and oppression of political and social opposition (United States Department of State, 2011). Cambodia's social framework is built on Theravada Buddhist foundations (Harris, 2012). Anti-human trafficking NGOs in Cambodia working to secure social justice outcomes operate at the mercy of, and in cooperation with, the authoritarian Cambodian government. In this authoritarian environment, these collaborative efforts between NGOs and the government have successfully identified human trafficking cases. While the identification of trafficking cases has improved over the last two decades, the number of women identified as trafficking victims who assert that they are not victims of trafficking but instead working in Cambodia's entertainment scene of their own free will is increasing (Keo et al., 2014; Overs, 2013; Steinfatt, 2011). While there are clear legal definitions of sex trafficking and human trafficking, interpretations of these definitions vary widely across anti-trafficking actors. Cultural, social, and political ideologies influence interpretations of these definitions. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of anti-trafficking efforts in Cambodia, it is essential to understand the origins and effects of beliefs, ideologies, and norms that drive government and NGO responses to human trafficking in Cambodia and the consequences of these on women engaging in the commercial sex industry or suspected of engaging in commercial sexual activity.

Significance

This study will contribute to filling the knowledge gap related to the origins and legitimization of anti-trafficking ideologies and practices in Cambodia and their effects on the agency and autonomy of women working in the commercial sex industry in Cambodia.

Research Questions

This study focuses on three research questions.

- 1) What are the cultural and ideological synergies between traditional Cambodian culture and Christianity related to female agency, morality, and sexuality?
- 2) How do these cultural and religious ideas shape responses to sex trafficking in Cambodia?
- 3) How do women working in the entertainment and commercial sex industries experience these anti-trafficking responses?

LITERATURE REVIEW

This research finds a foundation in Foucault's theory of power and discipline and its application to the lived experiences of women engaging in commercial sex in Cambodia.

Foucault's Theory of Power and Discipline

This study analyzes human trafficking interventions in Cambodia through the lens of Michel Foucault's theories of discipline and power. In his book *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of Prison* (1995), Foucault explores the emergence of societal discipline as a method of punishment

for disobedience. He argues, “Behind the disciplinary mechanisms can be read the haunting memory of ‘contagions,’ of the plague, of rebellions, crimes, vagabondage, desertions, people who appear and disappear, live and die in disorder” (Foucault, 1995, p. 198). Foucault’s idea of “contagions” gives language and depth to human fear of the unknown, and the potential of ‘the other’ to disrupt social order. He also likens discipline to the antithesis of a political plague of disorder. Discipline facilitates “regulation of the smallest details ... and the capillary functioning of power (Foucault, 1995, pp. 197-8). The functions of discipline are primarily applied to “abnormal individuals” whom Foucault typifies through the illustration of the leper and the plague (Foucault, 1995, p. 198).” Lepers are excluded from society, and the plague is eradicated through discipline. Excluding ‘lepers’ is a means of attaining the end goal of a “pure society,” while eradication of the plague through rigorous controls is a means of creating a “disciplined society” (Foucault, 1995, p. 198).

According to Foucault, power is enacted on the body, and the purpose of discipline is to make it “docile,” increase its utility, and bind its control to greater societal forces of governance (Foucault, 1995, pp. 136–137). “A body that is docile may be subjected, used, transformed, and improved” (Foucault, 1995, p. 135-6). Foucault (1995) underscores the role of societal institutions in democratizing the social construction of disciplinary practices through education, healthcare, and other institutional mechanisms, resulting in self-surveillance and adherence to societal norms.

Foucault’s explanations of the emotional experiences and social mechanisms that drive and facilitate stigmatization and othering, while relevant to the stigmatization and othering that occur as a result of human trafficking, have not yet been applied to these cases.

Gap in the Literature

This lack of direct application of Foucault's theory to current social issues related to stigma, othering, and the implementation of authoritarian discipline creates a gap in practical understanding of the cultural motivations and drivers of inequitable treatment of women engaged in sex work in Cambodia.

Definitions

Sex trafficking. "Sex trafficking is the recruitment, harboring, transportation, provision, obtaining, patronizing, or soliciting of a person for the purpose of a commercial sex act in which a commercial sex act is induced by force, fraud, or coercion, or in which the person induced to perform such act has not attained 18 years of age" (US Dept. of Justice, 2015).

Prostitution. Prostitution involves engaging, agreeing, or offering to engage in sexual conduct with another person in return for a fee (Cornell Law School, 2023).

This study will utilize the terminology of 'commercial sex' or 'sexual commerce' as a substitute for prostitution, as the author understands that 'prostitution' and 'prostitute' are highly stigmatized terms that have negative connotations regarding the legal status, dignity, and agency of women perceived to be engaging in commercial sexual activity.

METHODOLOGY

This study is a meta-analysis of NGO reports and scholarly articles on cultural and religious beliefs regarding women's agency and sexuality and sex trafficking in Cambodia. This study's scope is limited in that it only focuses on perceptions of women's agency, morality, and sexuality. It also analyzes sex trafficking responses in Cambodia. It analyzes scholarly literature focused on

cultural and religious constructions of social norms for women, sex trafficking responses in Cambodia, and the experiences of survivors of sex trafficking in Cambodia. A broader review of the literature on narratives surrounding prostitution and sex trafficking provides additional necessary context.

This study utilizes Foucault's (1995) theoretical framework to conduct a meta-analysis of scholarly literature documenting normative narratives on women's agency and sexuality in Cambodia, anti-sex trafficking responses in Cambodia, and the experiences of women working in the commercial sex industry in Cambodia related to the use of these tactics. Many scholarly articles explore human trafficking in Cambodia. However, much of this literature describes selected phenomena and histories of intervention in the country. The prevalence of phenomena-related studies creates an opportunity for a meta-analysis to identify themes that describe the social and political frameworks motivating social justice actors and constructing community development responses to human trafficking, as well as the effects of those responses on women working in the commercial sex industry in Cambodia.

FINDINGS

The author's review and analysis of existing literature on attitudes and beliefs about female sexuality in traditional Cambodian and Christian cultures and belief structures reveals important similarities between the two belief systems. The following sections examine the findings related to the research questions stated above. The first section explores the synergies between the two cultures regarding their beliefs about female agency, morality, and sexuality. The second section examines the effects of these beliefs on Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and government responses to sex trafficking in Cambodia. The third section details how women in

Cambodia experience anti-trafficking interventions. The paper concludes with a discussion of the application of Foucault's theory to the lived experiences of women engaging in commercial sex and anti-trafficking responses in Cambodia.

Cultural and Ideological Synergies Between Cambodian Culture and Christianity Related to Female Sexuality

The Value and Role of Women's Sexuality in Cambodia. The Chab Srey code, or "The Rules of the Lady" (Morrison, Lim, et al., 2021), is an institutionalized set of behavioral norms and expectations derived from an ancient 14th-century Cambodian poem presented as a mother's advice to her daughter. Over centuries, it has dictated women's value, roles, and sexuality in Cambodia (Anderson & Grace, 2018). The poem prescribes the behavior expected from "*Srei Kruap* Leakh (a woman full of virtue)" and how she should interact with three primary groups: her family, her husband, and others outside the home (Flude, 2013, p. 4). Schools in Cambodia taught the Chab Srey to girls enrolled in eighth and ninth grades until 2007, with an abbreviated, less formal version still taught in many schools (Anderson & Grace, 2018).

According to the Chab Srey, a virtuous woman never ventures far from her home, is always respectful and subservient to her husband, and honors her parents, caring and providing for them (Anderson & Grace, 2018; Flude, 2013; Morrison, Vanntheary, et al., 2021). A crucial aspect of the Chab Srey is the sexual propriety of a virtuous woman. A virtuous woman remains a virgin until married and, when married, maintains a monogamous sexual relationship in marriage no matter how promiscuous her husband is (Flude, 2013; Morrison et al., 2021). "Men are gold, women are cloth" is a common Cambodian saying that alludes to the belief that a woman who

violates social expectations and norms related to sexuality tarnishes her family's reputation forever. In contrast, a man's reputation is never questioned, no matter how promiscuous he is (Derks, 2008).

A woman who violates the rules of Chab Srey, especially the codes related to sexual morality and propriety, is labeled "*Srei Kouc* (the 'broken woman,')" a euphemism for a sex worker (Flude, 2013; Morrison, Vanntheary, et al., 2021). During Cambodia's colonial period, the French constructed a new identity for Cambodian women. The French perceived Cambodian women to be open to casual sexual relationships and interested in monetary rewards in exchange for sex (Jacobsen, 2008). As Cambodia sought to reestablish itself on the world stage in the wake of the Vietnam War, the coup and genocidal rule of the nationalist Khmer Rouge pursued a reclaiming of the sexuality of Cambodian women (Flude, 2013) to restore and maintain the purity of the nation. The end of the Khmer Rouge's reign over the country brought UN troops, foreign investment, and an increased demand for commercial sex (Derks, 2008). The identity of a prostitute or sex worker is culturally associated with "*Srei Kouc*," a woman broken and corrupted beyond repair or redemption who brings shame and dishonor to her family, community, and nation (Jacobsen, 2008). Jacobsen (2008) shows that staunch advocates for Cambodian culture viewed this new reality where commercial sex became more common as a "contamination" of Cambodian culture and a subversion of the culture's core values, causing women to fail in their role of "preserving" the values of the culture.

The Value and Role of Women's Sexuality in Christianity. The norms associated with the role and value of women's sexuality in Christianity originate in the Bible. In Genesis's narrative of the origins of human existence, a woman (Eve) is created to fulfill the relational needs of the man (Adam). Eve disobeys her creator, who then curses her. "Your desire shall be for your husband, and he shall rule over you." (*YouVersion*, 2023). In Genesis, male sexuality is prioritized,

and women are created for men's pleasure. The male controls women's sexuality, and the female "womb" is a tool for furthering male genetic lines (Mbuwayesango, 2016). In Biblical discourse on sex, "men are the active partners" and "it is men who 'know' women and women who are 'known'" (Mbuwayesango, 2016). Men are the only ones with "freedom, purpose, and activity," a woman who acts in "freedom" is sinful (Wu, n.d.)

The statements "purity before marriage" and "fidelity within marriage" (Hollinger, 2009, p. 30) summarize Modern Christian beliefs regarding sex. Sex must be "within marriage, exclusive, intimate, fruitful (reproductive), selfless, complex, and complementary" (Hollinger, 2009, p. 31). These requirements mean no sex outside of marriage. Sex is only appropriate between one man and one woman, and commercial selling of sex or other forms of sexual sin are forbidden. Therefore, a virtuous Christian woman abstains from any sexual activity until married and then only engages in sex with her husband. A woman who has sex outside of marriage has sinned (Hollinger, 2009).

The Bible frames sex workers as being "sinful and disloyal," unworthy of dignity or respect (Fones, 2022). Leviticus 19:29 states, "Do not profane your daughter by making her a prostitute, that the land not become prostituted and full of depravity" (*YouVersion*, 2023), implying that a woman's virtue has implications for the purity and character of the nation, not just herself and her family. Additionally, the act of prostitution is used as a metaphor to describe the circumstances in which the nation of Israel disobeyed God (Fones, 2022). The Bible regularly uses a narrative of prostitutes and sex workers that frames them as the source of social problems to which the use of violence (stoning) to purify society is justified. In the biblical context, prostitutes are subject to shame, ridicule, and direct and structural violence. They only become valuable when they have been 'saved' and returned to righteousness and conformity to social, cultural, and religious norms

(Fones, 2022). Jesus' interaction with a woman caught in adultery, whom he saved from being stoned for her sins and commanded to "Go, and sin no more" (Bible Gateway, 2024), exemplifies the limitations of Christian kindness where acc conditional on repentance.

Jesus had multiple interactions with women who are commonly understood to be sexual sinners. In each interaction, he was kind and respectful to the women, but his message was clear: they needed to repent of their sins and stop engaging in sexual immorality. His relationship with Mary of Magdalene, a woman often characterized as a former prostitute in Christian lore, is often used to exemplify the redemptive power of Christianity. However, her status as a former prostitute is a result of inferred identity based on surrounding passages rather than decisive labeling in the text (Carrol, 2006). So, despite Jesus' kindness toward women identified as sexual sinners, his interactions with them uphold the moral responsibility of women to remain sexually pure and maintain the patriarchal disparity regarding responsibility and accountability for sexual promiscuity within the Christian tradition.

Effects of Cultural Norms on Anti-Trafficking Responses and Tactics

Representations and Understandings of Sex Trafficking. There are profound differences in ideology related to what constitutes sex trafficking. Conservative and fundamentalist ideologies of social justice adhere to a belief that it is impossible for a person not under duress or coercion to choose to engage in commercial sex and consequently view all forms of commercial sex work and related activities as sex trafficking. Liberal ideologies and perspectives on social justice hold space for individual agency and choice and accordingly understand that there is a need for distinction between willing engagement in commercial sex work and forced sexual exploitation, sex

trafficking, and sexual slavery (Baker, 2013; Bernstein, 2010; Bettio et al., 2017; Brysk, 2009; Cojocaru, 2015; Swartz, 2019; Weitzer, 2007a).

The conservative ideology outlined above has largely shaped global legal frameworks, intervention design, and social discourse related to sex trafficking. In the United States, narratives of white slavery were codified into the Mann Act of 1910, which forbids the transportation of women across state lines for “immoral purposes.” This narrative and legislation facilitated the criminalization of ‘deviant’ sexual practices like interracial sex and other socially unacceptable sexual relationships (Baker, 2013). Doezema (1999) demonstrates there were two primary narratives associated with white slavery, “regulation” and “abolition.” Those in favor of regulation understood prostitution to be a “necessary evil” that was provided first by “fallen women” and later by “sexual deviants.” Abolitionists embraced a feminist approach that framed unrestricted male desire for sex as the primary problem and advocated for the “rescue and rehabilitation” of prostitutes rather than regulation or criminal prosecution. The abolitionist movement against prostitution eventually intensified into a campaign for social purity (Doezema, 1999). The framing of prostitution as white slavery was intentional as it removed female agency from the equation, highlighted stolen innocence, and removed the element of choice. This framing of prostitution and the agency or lack thereof for people involved in sexual commerce remains deeply embedded in current discussions of sex trafficking (Bettio et al., 2017). The prohibitions against prostitution remain in most national and international laws, and the ideology permeates anti-trafficking work. A notable example of the continued prevalence of this ideological approach is the US government’s requirement that anti-trafficking organizations receiving US Government funds must not advocate for the legalization of prostitution (Chuang, 2023).

When all commercial sex work is narrated as sex trafficking, the greater public demands a compelling solution (Twis & Praetorius, 2021; Weitzer, 2007b). Since 2000, the propagation of this ideology has resulted in an ever-growing number of social justice NGOs taking up the fight against sex trafficking around the world, with the rescue of ‘helpless’ victims of sex trafficking from exploitative situations being the most common and publicly salient model for addressing the problem (Jones et al., 2018; Swartz, 2019).

Prostitution and Sex Trafficking in Cambodia. Cheryl Overs (2013), in her report *From Sex Work to Entertainment and Trafficking: Implications of a Paradigm Shift for Sexuality, Law and Activism in Cambodia* introduces Cambodia’s 2008 adoption of a new anti-trafficking law with background on the impetus for its construction and implementation. She argues that pressure from the United States Government triggered Cambodia’s 2008 update to its anti-trafficking legal framework that made all commercial sex activities illegal as a method of addressing human and sex trafficking in the country. The language of the resulting law was ambiguous regarding the distinction between commercial sex work and sex trafficking, forcing women caught in or suspected of engaging in commercial sex into one of two sides of a legal dichotomy. The ambiguity of the law allows law enforcement the option of categorizing women suspected of sex work as trafficking victims or criminals, where those identified as trafficking victims are still often denied agency during their recovery process (Maher et al., 2015, p. 3). Concurrently, women engaging in the commercial sex economy are forced to contend with social and economic dichotomies as well. Economically, they can engage in the commercial sex economy and provide for themselves and their family, or they can suffer through poverty. Poverty leaves them unable to meet their needs or forces them to work in other physically demanding jobs, which also carry a risk of exploitation. Socially, they must choose between supporting their parents as dutiful daughters (Smith-Brake et

al., 2021) or maintaining their status as virtuous women. The choice to engage in commercial sex to fulfill their obligation as a dutiful daughter results in their stigmatization as a “broken woman” (Ditmore, 2014; Smith-Brake et al., 2021).

Figure 1
Summarizing Competing Ideologies on Sex Trafficking

Practical Approach	Morality Approach
Regulation	Abolition
Liberal	Christian and Conservative Feminist
Prostitution and sex trafficking are related but separate issues.	Prostitution is always sex trafficking.
Women can choose to engage in commercial sex.	No woman would ever choose to engage in commercial sex.
Women engaging in sexual commerce need regulations and legislation to protect them.	Women engaging in sexual commerce need to be rescued and rehabilitated.
Sex work is a valid economic choice.	Sex work is a crime and a violation of society’s moral standards.
Women engaging in commercial sex are dutiful daughters caring for their families.	Women engaging in commercial sex are broken women in need of rehabilitation and redemption.

Women’s Experiences with Anti-Trafficking Interventions

Beyond the consequences of political dichotomies that forced women to choose between the identities of victim or criminal, the implementation of the law had considerable tangible

consequences for women engaging in commercial sex and for public health campaigns in Cambodia (Overs, 2013). The construction of the 2008 anti-trafficking law reflects the influence of the underlying cultural belief that women who engage in sex outside of marriage, especially commercial sex, are defiled and broken women who tarnish the reputation of their families, communities, and culture (Jacobsen, 2008). One of the most prominent and tangible effects of this belief, in conjunction with the 2008 law, is the shift in Cambodian methods of policing women engaging in commercial sex and women suspected of engaging in commercial sex. After the 2008 law went into effect, brothels were closed, and street prostitution was highly policed, forcing the market for sex into other entertainment venues like bars, beer gardens, and KTV (karaoke) establishments where women negotiate privately with patrons wanting sexual services (Ditmore, 2014; Overs, 2013). As a result of brothel closures, commercial sex negotiations and transactions were pushed into these public venues, opening them up to increased scrutiny from law enforcement. Police in Phnom Penh regularly search women in entertainment districts and venues for condoms. If condoms are found on the woman or any man who is accompanying them, the woman is taken into custody (Overs, 2013). For women engaging in commercial sex, the stigma of their “*srei kouc* (broken woman)” identity has resulted in a disregard for their human rights and an escalation of police violence against sex workers (Ditmore, 2014; Maher et al., 2015; Overs, 2013). Ditmore (2014, p. 29) provides the following quote from a woman in Phnom Penh.

Chanta: “Violence has increased, especially from the police. The police look down on sex workers in the Garden and treat us like animals (Ditmore, 2014, p. 29).” Many women felt targeted as part of a larger plot to eliminate sex workers from society, as depicted in the quote below from Maher et al., (2015).

Chakriya, 22: “They want to abolish sex workers, so they catch us in order to send us for education and stop working like this. There are many jobs we can do. They don’t want us to do like this because it affects Khmer culture and tradition.” (Maher et al., 2015, p. 106)

Women who are arrested or rescued can face physical and sexual violence in police custody before being placed in government shelters or NGO shelters. Additionally, Overs (2013, p. 13) cites multiple sources detailing law enforcement’s use of the 2008 anti-trafficking law to police “indecent acts that affect morality, tradition, and public order,” with those detained forced to sign a pledge to rehabilitate and become good citizens. The current legal framework allows women who are taken into custody for commercial sexual activity to be classified as trafficked, which aligns with the philosophy and worldview of the predominately Christian NGOs fighting sex trafficking in Cambodia (Miles et al., 2021). Law enforcement officers often coordinate raids with NGOs, with NGOs functioning as informants, identifying potential victims, and providing shelter care for rescued women (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018). Many women dispute that they are trafficking victims and in need of rescue (Derks, 2008; Sandy, 2006). The following quote from a woman who was arrested and taken to a shelter against her will is an excellent example of the conflict between women perceived to be sex workers or sex trafficking victims and law enforcement and NGOs working to address sex trafficking.

Da, female, 2016: “They asked me, was I forced or treated badly. I did not know what they had to force me to do. I did not know. I applied to work there by myself. Then they said I told them a lie. I told them I did not tell them a lie. What was the problem? I did not know... They said that was ok although I did not know. They asked how old was I? I said I was older. I was 19 years old at that time. They said I was 15 or 16 years old and

then I was sent to an organization. I told them that I was 19 years old, but they did not believe me. They said I was 15 or 16 years old, so I did not know how I should say. After that, they sent me to the organization (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018).”

Women entering shelter care environments can find the process of entering and adjusting to life in shelters for survivors traumatizing. Once admitted to government or NGO shelters, survivors often encounter rigid, disciplinary environments that place considerable restrictions on their rights and freedoms and force participation in rehabilitation programs focused on breaking their dependence on commercial sex work and preparing them to engage in respectable employment after their release (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018). In the shelter environments, women experienced restrictions on their freedom of movement, use of the phone or internet, and ability to contact their families.

Sokchea, female, 2015: “They block us. Even the small window was blocked, too. In short, they tried to prevent us. I know they are trying to keep us safe, but it is too much... They have a lot of rules. I cannot even see the outsiders when I go out. In the previous time, when I went to get a training course offered by the shelter, I saw a man and he looked at me too, so I have to meet them in the office because of it. It wasn’t serious – I just looked at his face.... [We are monitored] 24 hours, except for the time I go to the restroom only. I am telling you the truth (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018, p. 20).”

In one government shelter, women were forced to grow vegetables, while in NGO shelters, women were often required to work in the NGOs’ social enterprises as a form of vocational training or rehabilitation. (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018; Overs, 2013).

Veatha, female, 2016: “I think the skill of sewing the wallet is not usable in Cambodia, as all the products were sent to abroad. I think it is impossible for me to do it in Cambodia (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018, p. 151).”

Additionally, many women reported that some of the staff in the shelters held stigmatized views of the shelter residents and verbally abused them. While women’s experiences in shelter care and training were mixed, many found the experience helpful despite their frustrations with how they came to reside in the shelter and its disciplinary structures (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018). In contrast to the negative experiences of women captured above, many women had positive experiences in recovery shelters and rehabilitation programs.

Bormey, female, 2016: “It [support from the shelter] changes me a lot. I think if I do not receive support from the shelter, I might not have everything I have today. They treated me and supported me for studying too... I could study until grade 12” (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018, p. 75)

Monyrath, female, 2016: “They [the staff] were kind. They never blamed us... They treated me in a good way. When I lived in that room, my housemother told me to be patient. I could change my attitude because my attitude was not good, as I did not listen to other-people’s speech... When she taught me like that, I changed my attitude. She told me and encouraged me. I listened to her when she spoke. I changed.” (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018, p. 78)

Researchers have also documented survivors’ positive experiences with shelter staff.

Rachana, 2016: “The teachers who worked in the shelter, as well as the counselor, encouraged me a lot. Those mums there encouraged me and I felt warmer than staying at

home. I did not feel warm when I lived with my family, but I felt warm when I stayed in the shelter. They took care of me all the time. . . I do not mean they took care of my body, but they taught me and used soft words” (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2020, p. 183).

The experiences of survivors shared above are just a small sampling of many experiences documented through the Butterfly Longitudinal Research project on survivor experiences in Cambodia conducted by Chab Dai, an international Anti-trafficking organization working in Cambodia, and a growing series of papers resulting from the data collected and research from other scholars like Maher et al., (2015). As a collective whole, the reports from the butterfly project and the scholarly research resulting from the study show that survivor experiences range from positive and impactful to negative and traumatizing. This diversity of experiences in shelter environments and the public stigma that come with being identified as a broken woman make being identified as a trafficking victim and forced into the rehabilitation system an experience fraught with risk.

Figure 3

Influences on Sex Trafficking Responses in Cambodia

DISCUSSION

The alignment of Cambodian social norms, Christian anti-prostitution and anti-sex trafficking ideologies, and international political pressure from the US government to address sex trafficking in Cambodia created the opportunity for a disciplinary approach to addressing sex trafficking in Cambodia. Government and NGO responses to sex trafficking in Cambodia align with Foucault's (1995) theory of discipline as outlined in his book *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*. Foucault's primary theory that "power is enacted on the body" (Foucault, 1995, pp. 136–137) is powerfully relevant in relationship to women perceived to be engaged in commercial sex work in Cambodia and the desire of social, religious, and political forces to control their use of their bodies as a commodity for sexual commerce.

International pressure from the US Government to address sex trafficking in the country under threat of the discontinuation of aid funding to the country (Keo et al., 2014; Overs, 2013) created political space to address the social contagion of commercial sex work in Cambodia. This political cover to address sex trafficking resulted in the adoption of authoritarian disciplinary approaches based on the equivocation of prostitution with sex trafficking in NGO and government narratives. While there are definite international legal distinctions between prostitution and sex trafficking, narratives equating prostitution and sex trafficking in Cambodia are used to legitimize law enforcement's harassment and privacy invasion of women suspected of being involved in commercial sexual activity (prostitution). The harassment and search of women's persons and belongings on the street looking for condoms or other indications that a woman has engaged in or intends to engage in commercial sex, as documented (Overs, 2013), serves to regulate the "smallest details" of their lives and exemplifies the "capillary functioning of power" over their daily lives (Foucault, 1995, p.198). Ultimately, law enforcement's targeting of women carrying condoms has resulted in Cambodian women working in the entertainment industry engaging in self-surveillance and self-regulation to the point where they no longer feel comfortable carrying condoms to protect themselves (Maher et al., 2015; Overs, 2013). Cambodian authority's adoption of prostitution equals sex trafficking philosophy, and their invasion of women's privacy and infringement on their right to possess simple human necessities like condoms results in a denial of women's agency. It also limits access to essential health care for women participating in or perceived to be participating in sexual commerce. This policy and its implementation increase the risk of a recurrence of the HIV epidemic in Cambodia (Maher et al., 2015; Overs, 2013).

Cambodian women who work in the entertainment sector are socially understood to be engaging in sexual commerce (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018; Derks, 2008; Ditmore, 2014; Flude,

2013; Morrison et al., 2021; Sandy, 2006) and therefore construed as “abnormal individuals” (Foucault, 1995, p. 198) who must be reformed or rehabilitated to eliminate the spread of “the contagion” into social disorder. In the case of Cambodian women engaged in sexual commerce or trafficked for sex, the contagion responses of exclusion and discipline are applied in succession and in tandem. ‘Trafficked’ women, who are identified through “observation” and “examination” (Foucault, 1995, pp. 170–194), are placed in a state of exclusion and subjected to regimented disciplinary environments to purify society by excluding the abnormality and subsequently reforming the ‘abnormal’ individual into a new “docile body” that is ready to be utilized and governed by a “disciplined society” (Foucault, 1995, pp. 136–137).

While exclusion and discipline play vital roles in maintaining a healthy society, it is crucial to interrogate when they are used and what narratives and socio-cultural belief structures are used to legitimize their implementation, especially when their usage adversely affects the human rights of a particular group, increasing their marginalization. In the case of Cambodia, perceptions of the capacity for agency in women identified as victims of sex trafficking under the current legal framework vary widely between ideologies, resulting in disagreements regarding the actual number of sex trafficking victims in Cambodia. Keo et al. (2014) and Steinfatt (2011) found that estimates of human trafficking and sex trafficking in Cambodia were unreliable, inaccurate, and often heavily inflated. Definitions are pivotal to prevalence debates related to sex trafficking, with the debate over whether voluntary prostitution should be considered sex trafficking taking center stage. Steinfatt's research (2011) documented NGO claims alleging the number of women trafficked for sex in Cambodia to be somewhere between 40,000 and 80,000 and presented evidence to debunk these estimates. Steinfatt's empirical survey (2011, p. 458) and calculations of women working in sexual commerce in Cambodia in 2008 estimated that 27,925 women were

engaged in commercial sexual activity. Of those, only 1,058 were victims of sex trafficking. (Figure 2) The differences between NGO and academic estimates detailed above highlight the importance of definitions; if commercial sex work is always only sex trafficking, the scale of the problem of sex trafficking in Cambodia is considerable and shocking. However, if sex trafficking is a distinct, separate, and considerably more serious crime, the scope and scale of the sex trafficking problem in Cambodia is dramatically smaller.

Figure 2
Disparity in Sex Trafficking Prevalence Estimates in Cambodia

NGO Estimates	Empirical Academic Research
	27,975 women engaged in commercial sexual activity (Steinfatt, 2011)
40,000 - 80,000 Sex trafficking victims (Steinfatt, 2011)	1,058 Victims of sex trafficking (Steinfatt, 2011)

This ideological debate is where Cambodian women’s right to agency and self-determination collides with social justice agendas, cultural norms, religious ideologies, and international politics. In defiance of overwhelming rhetoric and social norms that delegitimize sex work as a choice and deny their capacity for agency, many Cambodian women engaging in commercial sex in Cambodia are doing so with full agency and intent (Cordisco Tsai et al., 2018; Derks, 2008; Flude, 2013; Sandy, 2006). Sandy's research (2006) with Cambodian women selling sex demonstrated that women often move in and out of sex work as required to maintain their desired lifestyles, provide for their families, or avoid other less preferable forms of labor like working in brick kilns or garment factories. While their stories do not demonstrate access to

unrestricted economic choices, they do reflect intentional actions that allow women to create a life of their choosing and provide for their loved ones (Sandy, 2006).

Christianity and normative Cambodian culture relegate Cambodian women who engage in sexual commerce to a space that denies them agency and autonomy over their bodies. These cultures, which self-identify as vastly different in values and belief structures, find considerable common ground concerning their views on women's values, virtue, and sexuality. Narratives from Christian NGOs and activists demonize the Cambodian culture for its devaluing of women, adherence to filial piety, and perceived willingness to sell their daughters for sex. However, comparisons of cultural values related to women's value, sexuality, and agency find that Christianity and traditional Cambodian culture are built on the same patriarchal foundations that relegate women to submissive, domestic roles where they are expected to provide for their families, submit to the husband's authority, and maintain their virtue and fidelity at all times.

The synergy of these alignments with social justice anti-prostitution and sex trafficking narratives has resulted in severe violations of women's rights. Women who violate these norms face stigmatizing rhetoric from both local Cambodian culture and Christian NGO culture, with both depicting women who have been 'trafficked' as broken women who are victims in need of recovery care, rehabilitation, and reforming to meet social and cultural expectations and norms. While NGOs critique the authoritarian nature of the Cambodian regime, its authoritarian disciplinary practices used to address 'sex trafficking' are applauded for their effectiveness in reducing prostitution and sex trafficking in the country. Many social justice and community development NGOs use the cover of Cambodia's disciplinary practices and international anti-prostitution rhetoric to legitimize their own disciplinary programming that ignores women's agency.

Both Cambodian and Christian patriarchal cultural norms legitimize authoritarian responses to commercial sex work in Cambodia under the guise of anti-sex trafficking efforts, leading to significant violations of women's rights and freedoms and the rights and freedoms of their spouses and partners.

CONCLUSION

This paper has explored the cultural beliefs and practices related to women's sexuality in Cambodian and Christian cultures. It then examined the effects of these beliefs on the nature of anti-sex trafficking interventions in Cambodia, the experiences of women engaged in commercial sexual activity, and women's experiences with anti-sex trafficking interventions in Cambodia. It then applies Foucault's theory of power and discipline to the context of anti-sex trafficking interventions in Cambodia and women's experiences with these interventions.

RQ1: Cultural and ideological synergies between Cambodian culture and Christianity related to female agency and sexuality

The anti-trafficking environment in Cambodia is co-constructed by a complex web of social, cultural, religious, and political actors with varying motivations for influencing and controlling women's agency over their choices, bodies, and economic activities. Both traditional Cambodian culture and the Christian beliefs of many NGOs in the country narrate an ideal social reality that is patriarchal. Where women's agency, morality, and sexuality are subject to the moral judgments of men, and women's active use of sexual agency tarnishes their reputation, the honor of their families, and the integrity and honor of the nation.

RQ2: Cultural and religious shaping of sex trafficking responses in Cambodia

The legitimization of authoritarian discipline for social and moral cleansing in Cambodia as anti-sex trafficking interventions through cultural, religious, and political rhetoric equating prostitution and sex trafficking has resulted in the government and NGOs denying women agency.

RQ3: Women's experiences with anti-trafficking responses in Cambodia

This denial of women's agency has resulted in infringements on their human rights, invasions of their privacy, and their subjection to disciplinary environments in government and NGO shelters that align with Foucault's explanation of social disciplinary systems, their purposes, and their tactics. Forcing women to work on government farms and NGO 'social enterprises' as part of their rehabilitation demonstrates the "subjection" and "use" of women's bodies for the gain of others under the guise of discipline meant to improve their moral purity and capacity for social good (Foucault, 1995).

While these tactics are reducing the prevalence of visible commercial sex transactions in Cambodia and helping women find alternatives to provide for themselves and their families, they also exercise significant control over women's lives. Existing research and socio-cultural narratives on Cambodian culture and anti-trafficking NGOs suggest a desire to control women's expressions of sexuality and deny their ability to engage in commercial sex willfully. The desire of cultural purists and moral abolitionists to maintain moral purity, a disciplined society, and the public honor of the nation are also significant factors driving this conflict between women working in the commercial sex industry and anti-trafficking actors. Ethnographic research with women engaging in commercial sex work in Cambodia reveals that women engage in commercial sex as a result of a complex matrix of economic, social, and personal preference factors and that many

women exercise considerable agency as they move in and out of commercial sex work over many years (Derks, 2008; Sandy, 2006). See Figure 1 below.

Social, cultural, and religious norms and narratives denying the agency of all women engaged in commercial sex work, in combination with the disciplinary approach to sex trafficking interventions and the rehabilitation of women, has resulted in an increased risk of violence towards women in the commercial sex industry, a significant reduction of safe sex practices increasing their chances of contracting STDs and AIDS, and reduced these women's ability to provide for themselves and their families while failing to help many women exit "trafficking" situations permanently (Miles et al., 2021). Furthermore, the continued use of narratives identifying women engaging in sexual commerce as trafficking victims without regard for individual circumstances and choices is an act of rhetorical violence that diminishes their perceived value in society, reduces their access to opportunities and social support systems, and results in increased risks of other forms of violence.

RECOMMENDATIONS

There is a need to improve government and NGO responses to sex trafficking in Cambodia. These needs can be grouped into three categories: clarifying anti-trafficking legislation, improving oversight on anti-trafficking responses and interventions, and improving social and cultural narratives related to sex trafficking. Overall, there are five recommendations related to legislation, policy, and implementation, as well as two recommendations for improving social and cultural narratives.

Clarifying Anti-trafficking Legislation

1. Update anti-trafficking legislation to clearly differentiate between voluntary commercial sexual activity and sex trafficking.

2. Ensure women's right to privacy and freedom from arbitrary search and detention and involuntary assignment to anti-trafficking shelters.

Improving Oversight on Anti-Trafficking Responses

1. Ensure law enforcement and anti-trafficking NGOs understand the difference between voluntary commercial sexual activity and sex trafficking.
2. Ensure that women who are confirmed to be trafficked can maintain their agency throughout the recovery process.
3. Initiate required training for Law enforcement, judiciary, and NGO actors on trauma-informed care, survivor's right to freedom and agency, and ethical representation of women survivors and women engaged in commercial sexual activity.

Improving Social and Cultural Narratives

1. Implement social awareness and advocacy campaigns affirming women's rights and healthy understandings of women's agency and sexuality.
2. Implement public awareness campaigns that place the stigma of trafficking on perpetrators rather than female survivors of trafficking.

Closing Remarks

While human trafficking and sex trafficking are considerable problems in Cambodia and the trafficking of even one woman, man, or child is one too many, it is essential to constantly review and evaluate social norms and attitudes, government and NGO responses, and the impacts of these

social justice initiatives on those they intend to help. The literature depicting anti-sex trafficking responses in Cambodia is overwhelmingly clear that anti-trafficking responses are having adverse unintended consequences on many women. Amid efforts to eradicate sex trafficking in Cambodia, women are suffering due to misaligned authoritarian approaches that have lost their connection to the purpose of their existence: to improve the lives of women, their access to human rights, agency, and a hopeful future. This lost connection and its unintended consequences are the result of social and cultural rhetoric and discourse that values patriarchal power over women more than empowering women.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, E., & Grace, K. (2018). From Schoolgirls to “Virtuous” Khmer Women: Interrogating Chhab Srey and Gender in Cambodian Education Policy. *Studies in Social Justice, 12*(2).
- Baker, C. N. (2013). Moving Beyond “Slaves, Sinners, and Saviors”: An Intersectional Feminist Analysis of US Sex-Trafficking Discourses, Law and Policy. *Journal of Feminist Scholarship, 4*(4).
- Bernstein, E. (2010). Militarized Humanitarianism Meets Carceral Feminism: The Politics of Sex, Rights, and Freedom in Contemporary Antitrafficking Campaigns. *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society, 36*(1), 45–71. <https://doi.org/10.1086/652918>
- Bettio, F., Della Giusta, M., & Di Tommaso, M. L. (2017). Sex Work and Trafficking: Moving beyond Dichotomies. *Feminist Economics, 23*(3), 1–22.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2017.1330547>
- Bible Gateway. (2024). *John 8:1-11—New Living Translation*. Bible Gateway.
<https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=John%208%3A1-11&version=NLT>
- Brysk, A. (2009). Beyond Framing and Shaming: Human Trafficking, Human Security and Human Rights. *Journal of Human Security, 5*(3), 8–21.
<https://doi.org/10.3316/JHS0503008>
- Carrol, J. (2006). *Who Was Mary Magdalene?* Smithsonian Magazine.
<https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/who-was-mary-magdalene-119565482/>
- Chuang, J. A. (2023). *RESCUING TRAFFICKING FROM IDEOLOGICAL CAPTURE: PROSTITUTION REFORM AND ANTI-TRAFFICKING LAW AND POLICY*.
- Clawson, H. J. (2007). Estimating Human Trafficking Into The United States: Development of a Methodology Final Phase Two Report. *ICF International Report*.

- Cojocaru, C. (2015). Sex trafficking, captivity, and narrative: Constructing victimhood with the goal of salvation. *Dialectical Anthropology*, 39(2), 183–194.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10624-015-9366-5>
- Cordisco Tsai, L., Vanntheary, L., & Nhanh, C. (2018). *Experiences in Shelter Care: Perspectives from Participants in the Butterfly Longitudinal Study*. (p. 208) [NGO]. Chab Dai.
- Cordisco Tsai, L., Vanntheary, Li., & Channtha, N. (2020). Perspectives of Survivors of Human Trafficking and Sexual Exploitation on Their Relationships with Shelter Staff: Findings from a Longitudinal Study in Cambodia. *The British Journal Of Social Work*, 50, 176–194. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjsw/bcz128>
- Cornell Law School. (2023). *Prostitution*. LII / Legal Information Institute.
<https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/prostitution>
- Derks, A. (2008). *Khmer women on the move: Exploring work and life in urban Cambodia*. Univ. of Hawai'i Press.
- Ditmore, M. H. (2014). “Caught Between the Tiger and the Crocodile”: Cambodian Sex Workers’ Experiences of Structural and Physical Violence. *Studies in Gender and Sexuality*, 15(1), 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15240657.2014.877726>
- Doezema, J. (1999). Loose women or lost women? The re-emergence of the myth of white slavery in contemporary discourses of trafficking in women. *Gender Issues*, 18(1), 23–50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12147-999-0021-9>
- Flude, C. (2013). ‘Women are like white cloth, once soiled with mud; it can be washed but never made clean again’: The Srei Kouc ('broken woman’) in Cambodian society and her

unlikely agency through the ‘girlfriend experience’;

https://www.academia.edu/15770400/_Women_are_like_white_cloth_once_soiled_with_mud_it_can_be_washed_but_never_made_clean_again_The_Srei_Kouc_broken_woman_in_Cambodian_society_and_her_unlikely_agency_through_the_girlfriend_experience

Fones, B. (2022). Reading in and Writing Out: Origins and Impacts of Approaches to Sex Work in Biblical and Theological Scholarship. In T. Sanders, K. McGarry, & P. Ryan (Eds.), *Sex work, Labour, and relation: New Directions and Reflections*. Springer International Publishing.

Foucault, M. (1995). *DISCIPLINE AND PUNISH* (A. Sheridan, Trans.). Vintage Books.

Harris, I. (2012). Buddhism in Cambodia Since 1993. In P. Sothirak, G. Wade, & M. Hong (Eds.), *Cambodia: Progress and challenges since 1991*. Inst. of Southeast Asian Studies.

Hollinger, D. P. (2009). *The Meaning of Sex: Christian Ethics and the Moral Life*. Baker Academic.

International Labor Organization. (2024, January 28). *Child Labour | International Labour Organization*. <https://www.ilo.org/projects-and-partnerships/projects/child-labour>

Jacobsen, T. (2008). *Lost goddesses: The denial of female power in cambodian history*. NIAS Press.

Jones, S., King, J., & Edwards, N. (2018). Human-trafficking prevention is not “sexy”: Impact of the rescue industry on Thailand NGO programs and the need for a human rights approach. *Journal of Human Trafficking*, 4(3), 231–255.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/23322705.2017.1355161>

- Keo, C., Bouhours, T., Broadhurst, R., & Bouhours, B. (2014). Human Trafficking and Moral Panic in Cambodia. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 653(1), 202–224. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716214521376>
- Lawrence, B. (2020). *Outlawing Opposition, Imposing Rule of Law: Authoritarian Constitutionalism in Cambodia*.
- Luo, J. J., & Un, K. (2022). Organizational Strength and Authoritarian Durability in Cambodia. *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*, 55(4), 59–82. <https://doi.org/10.1525/cpcs.2022.1627857>
- Maher, L., Dixon, T. C., Phlong, P., Mooney-Somers, J., Stein, E. S., & Page, K. (2015). Conflicting Rights: How the Prohibition of Human Trafficking and Sexual Exploitation Infringes the Right to Health of Female Sex Workers in Phnom Penh, Cambodia. *Health and Human Rights*, 17(1), 102. <https://doi.org/10.2307/healhumarigh.17.1.102>
- Mbuwayesango, D., R. (2016). Sex and Sexuality in Biblical Narrative. In *The Oxford Handbook of Biblical Narrative* (pp. 456–464). Oxford University Press.
- Miles, G. M., Havey, J., Miles, S., Piano, E., Vannthey, Li., Channtha, N., Phaly, S., & Sopheara, O. (2021). “I Don’t Want the Next Generation of Children to Be in Pain Like Me”: The Chab Dai Ten-Year Butterfly Longitudinal Research Project on Sex Trafficking Survivors in Cambodia. *Dignity: A Journal of Analysis of Exploitation and Violence*, 6(4). <https://doi.org/10.23860/dignity.2021.06.04.02>
- Miles, G. M., Vannthey, L., & Nhanh, C. (2020). *Children of the Wood Children of the Stone* (p. 84). Chab Dai. <https://www.chabdai.org/s/SpiritualityThematicPaper.pdf>
- Morrison, T., Lim, V., Channtha, N., Havey, J., & Miles, G. M. (2021). “You Have to Be Strong and Struggle”: Stigmas as a Determinants “You Have to Be Strong and Struggle”:

- Stigmas as a Determinants of Inequality for Female Survivors of Sex Trafficking in Cambodia of Inequality for Female Survivors of Sex Trafficking in Cambodia. *Dignity: A Journal of Analysis of Exploitation and Violence*, 6(4).
- Morrison, T., Vanntheary, L., Nhanh, C., Havey, J., & Miles, G. M. (2021). “You Have to Be Strong and Struggle”: Stigmas as a Determinants of Inequality for Female Survivors of Sex Trafficking in Cambodia. *Dignity: A Journal of Analysis of Exploitation and Violence*, 6(4).
- Overs, C. (2013). From Sex Work to Entertainment and Trafficking. *Evidence Report*, 23.
- Sandy, L. (2006). Sex Work in Cambodia: Beyond the Voluntary/Forced Dichotomy. *Asian and Pacific Migration Journal*, 15(4), 449–469.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/011719680601500402>
- Smith-Brake, J., Lim, V., International Organization for Migration, Cambodia, Chantha, N., & Mission Alliance, Cambodia. (2021). “Why Am I the Only One Responsible for the Whole Family?”: Expressions of Economic Filial Piety and Financial Anxiety Among Female Survivors of Sex Trafficking in Cambodia. *Dignity: A Journal of Analysis of Exploitation and Violence*, 6(4). <https://doi.org/10.23860/dignity.2021.06.04.05>
- Steinfatt, T. M. (2011). Sex trafficking in Cambodia: Fabricated numbers versus empirical evidence. *Crime, Law and Social Change*, 56(5), 443–462.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10611-011-9328-z>
- Swartz, D. R. (2019). “Rescue Sells”: Narrating Human Trafficking to Evangelical Populists. *The Review of Faith & International Affairs*, 17(3), 94–104.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15570274.2019.1644014>

The Associated Press. (2024, February 21). *Cambodia's new prime minister wins lawmakers' approval for his youngest brother to become his deputy*. AP News.

<https://apnews.com/article/hun-many-manith-manet-sen-nepotism-9f70d85a2668384ab1efeb82782c3f8f>

Twis, M., & Praetorius, R. (2021). A qualitative interpretive meta-synthesis of evangelical Christian sex trafficking narratives. *Journal of Religion & Spirituality in Social Work: Social Thought*, 40(2), 189–215. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15426432.2020.1871153>

United States Department of State. (2011). *CAMBODIA* (Country Reports on Human Rights Practices for 2011). Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights, and Labor.

US Dept. of Justice. (2015, October 6). *Human Trafficking | Human Trafficking*.

<https://www.justice.gov/humantrafficking>

Walk Free. (2023). *Global Slavery Index* (p. 172). <https://www.walkfree.org/global-slavery-index/>

Weitzer, R. (2007a). The Social Construction of Sex Trafficking: Ideology and Institutionalization of a Moral Crusade. *Politics & Society*, 35(3), 447–475.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0032329207304319>

Weitzer, R. (2007b). The Social Construction of Sex Trafficking: Ideology and Institutionalization of a Moral Crusade. *Politics & Society*, 35(3), 447–475.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0032329207304319>

Wu, R. (n.d.). Women on the Boundary: Prostitution, Contemporary and in the Bible. *Feminist Theology*.

YouVersion. (2023). <https://www.bible.com/bible/114/GEN.3.NKJV>